

Financial Analysis of Poultry Egg Production in Northern Region of Ghana

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Abstract

This study investigated the profitability of poultry egg production in selected districts of the Northern Region. Primary data was collected from 125 poultry farms across three purposively selected Districts in the Region. Structured questionnaire was used to solicit data for the study. With the aid of descriptive statistics, farm level data were analysed. Per the profit measures, the study revealed that poultry egg production in the study area was profitable as indicated by the average gross margin and the average net farm income. The challenges of business operations of poultry egg farmers were also examined. As underscored by the descriptive statistics, the serious constraints confronting the poultry egg farmers in the area in order of severity are; high cost of feeds, harsh weather conditions, high mortality rate, high cost of credit, cheap imported substitutes, poor market, poor extension and rising cost of day-old chicks. It is recommended that the government's agricultural policy of 'planting for food and jobs' be extended to poultry egg production to create sustainable jobs for the youth in the region towards poverty reduction and wealth creation.

Keywords: Profitability, poultry egg, constraints, financial efficiency, northern region.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is the main economic activity in Ghana, especially among the people in the northern part of the country (Alhassan, 2019). Farmers are primarily engaged in food crop production and animal husbandry for their livelihood. In spite of the heavy dependence on crop production, attention on poultry production is on the surge (Hafez et al. 2020). In recent times, the livestock sub-sector is one of the fastest growing agricultural sectors in Ghana (Ouma et al., 2019). The poultry industry offers great opportunities for job creation and improved livelihoods for farmers in many parts of the country. The economic significance of a vibrant poultry industry cannot be overemphasized. Besides the creation of direct job opportunities for the poultry famers, the industry offers indirect opportunities through backward and forward linkages (MoFA, 2020). The poultry value chain involves several players such as; feed producers and retailers, veterinary personnel, vaccines and drug producers and retailers, restaurants and food vendors, manure production for domestic use and sale, among others. Consequently, the poultry sector has greater potential for poverty alleviation, particularly in the poverty-stricken areas of the country, including Northern Region (Zamani et al. 2022). Furthermore, poultry constitutes the cheapest and effective source of animal protein for many families in Africa and other parts of the World (FAOSTATS 2020).

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Like many other industries, the poultry industry is categorized into large-scale commercial enterprises, medium-scale businesses and small-scale operators (Janet et al. 2020). Majority of the poultry famers in the Northern Region are small-scale operators (Ghana Poultry Report, 2019). Almost all (about 87%) of the large and medium scale poultry businesses are located in the Bono, Ashanti and Greater Accra Regions (McGovern-Dole, 2016).

In broader terms, poultry consists of all domesticated feather species such as chicken, guinea fowls, quails, ducks, turkeys, ostriches, etc (Ghana Poultry Report, 2019). Poultry egg production is an emerging economic activity in the Northern Region; hence the focus of the study. The poultry industry in Ghana offers two (2) major product lines, namely; poultry eggs and poultry meat. Farmers who rear layers supply eggs while those rearing broilers supply meat. Both product lines have become more prominent in recent times due to increased demand for poultry eggs and meat (Ghana Poultry Report, 2019). The poultry market is highly competitive. Local farmers face stiff competition from imported poultry and poultry products (including frozen chicken). Kyekyeku (2018) reports that Ghanaian poultry farmers fail to compete favourably with cheap poultry imports from Brazil and United States of America, hence are operating below capacity. This state of affairs does not auger well for the advancement of the local poultry industry.

To remedy the poultry industry from collapse, some African countries have imposed import restrictions on poultry products. These import restrictions are primarily aimed at; boosting local production, curbing the outbreaks of animal diseases, and increasing self-sufficiency in the medium to long term (Naggujja et al., 2020; Johnson, 2011; Akunzule et al., 2009). In Ghana, the government has intermittently imposed import bans on poultry products from its trading partners, notably, Netherlands, Germany, Russia, Denmark, USA and the United Kingdom (Johnson, 2011). The government has also provided limited financial and technical support to local poultry producers to expand their operations. In July 2014 for instance, the Broiler Revitalization Project was launched. The aim of the project was to stimulate local broiler production in the country (Ghana Poultry Report, 2019). The current government has also provided limited financial support to selected local producers to expand their operations in line with the policy of 'Rearing for food and Jobs' which was launched in 2019 (MoFA, 2020). Similarly, a ban was imposed on poultry imports in the last quarter of 2020, in response to an outbreak of Avian Influenza subtype H5N8 in Europe. The United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) through the Ghana Poultry Program (GPP) has also launched a five-year (2015-2020) project which is being implemented by Agricultural Cooperative Development International (ACDI) and Volunteers in Overseas Cooperation Assistance (VOCA) and Technoserve to expand local egg production and processing of poultry meat in Ghana. The project aims at increasing the competitiveness of the local poultry value chain using inclusive system approach (Ghana Poultry Report, 2019). Furthermore, the government of Ghana has also launched a national egg consumption campaign dubbed "Egg-cite your day" to encourage Ghanaians to eat an egg a day (Njiru *et al.*, 2020). In spite of these policy measures designed to boost the local poultry sector, there still exist production bottlenecks (FAOSTAT, 2020).

In spite of the vital role of the poultry sector in the socioeconomic development of Ghana, it is bedeviled with numerous constraints. Some of the key constraints are; rising cost of production, stiff competition from highly subsidized foreign producers, inadequate availability of credit facilities, inefficient production and processing technologies and limited knowledge of modern production management (Netherlands Enterprise Agency, 2019; Ashitey, 2017).

The key challenge of the poultry farmers in the Northern Region is the rising cost of production. The major feed ingredients are maize, soya meal or fishmeal, wheat bran or rice bran, and vitamins. These feed products are produced locally or imported into the country. Largely, soya bean meal, fishmeal, and vitamin-mineral premixes used in feed production are imported while the white and yellow maize are produced locally. In the face of increasing demand for maize for both human consumption and animal feed, the price of the product is not only sky-rocketing but also scarce in the market, hence the importation of poultry feed products to supplement local

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production has been on the increase (Zamani et al. 2022). The implication is that, the volumes of imports far exceed local output (FAOSTAT, 2020). As a result of the depreciation of the local currency (Cedi) relative to the U.S Dollar, the cost of critical imported poultry feed products and equipment is at all-time high. The excessive imports of poultry and poultry feed products have significantly contributed to the dwindling self-sufficiency in most African countries, including Ghana (Asante Addo et al., 2020; Weible, 2020; Sumberg et al., 2017).

There have been many studies on poultry production in the Northern sector of the country, however, these studies are concentrated on the broiler sector of the poultry industry (Ettah et al., 2021; Ekong, 2015; Hassan et al., 2011). In this study, we seek to explore the layer sub-sector which supplies poultry eggs in the Region. The layer sub-sector faces less competition in the market compared to the broiler sub-sector where cheaper frozen chicken dominates the meat market (Janet, 2020).

The study is expected to provide insight into the emerging poultry industry in the region and to guide policy makers and other relevant stakeholders in the poultry value chain. The study is limited to the selected districts due to the concentration of small and medium scale poultry egg farmers as well as ease of access by the investigators.

2.0 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study seeks to;

Measure the profitability and financial efficiency of the poultry egg farmers in selected districts of the Northern Region and also identify and analyse the challenges that hinder the poultry egg farmers in their operations.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Collection

Primary data was taken from three purposively selected Districts/Metropolis in the Northern Region, namely, Tamale Metropolis, Sagnarigu Municipal and the Kumbugu District. This is because most of the poultry farms in the northern region are concentrated in those places. The concentration of the poultry farms in those locations was partly attributable to greater accessibility to markets, sources of water, reliable hydro-electric power, and other basic socio-economic amenities that are prerequisite in the poultry egg production. Data was collected from 125 poultry farms across the three selected Districts/Metropolis in the Region. The poultry farmers in the study area belong to the Poultry Farmers' Cooperative in the Northern Region. We obtained the list of poultry egg farmers in the region from the Farmers' Cooperative. Structured questionnaire was used to solicit data for the study. We used simple random technique to obtain relevant data from the farmers. Prior to the administration of the questionnaire on the respondents, the investigators conducted a pretest of the instrument on four (4) poultry farms in Gbolo-Kpalsi and Kpene in the Sagnarigu Municipality. The pretesting enabled the investigators to fine-tune the final questionnaire for the study. In-depth interviews and focus group discussions were held with executives of the Poultry Famers Co-operative in the Northern Region between January and May, 2022 to have a better understanding of the operations of the poultry farmers in the study area.

This study was guided by a number of assumptions;

- i. Small-scale and medium-scale poultry egg farms were considered. Poultry farms with between 100 and 500 bird flock were considered small-scale, and those farmers who reared between 501 and 1000 birds were considered as medium scale farmers.
- ii. Birds will produce eggs for 24-month production cycle, with the production of eggs starting when the birds (layers) are 18 weeks old.
- iii. Eggs produced are for commercial purposes
- iv. All available spent layers are due for disposal at the end of the 24-month production cycle.

3.2 Financial Analysis

Financial analysis provides basis for assessing the performance of a business enterprise. The performance of a business entity is either measured over time (time series) or measured against its competitors at a time (cross sectional). Financial analysis reveals the strengths and weaknesses of business enterprises and it is the most potent tool for evaluating the success or otherwise of business operations (Aown, 2021). The financial efficiency of the poultry egg enterprise is evaluated using four (4) financial ratios (Michael, 2020), namely; Operating Expense Ratio, Depreciation Expense Ratio, Net Farm Income Ratio, and Production Efficiency Ratio.

- i. Operating Expense Ratio is the proportion of revenue which is spent on operating expenses. It is estimated as;

$$\text{Operating Expense Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Operating Expenses} - \text{Depreciation}}{\text{Gross Revenue}} \times 100\%$$

The lower the Operating Expense Ratio the better the business operations; since it implies that a lower proportion of the gross revenue is spent on the operating expenses, thereby allowing the business owner(s) to retain a greater proportion of the revenue. The reverse is valid for a higher Operating Expense Ratio.

- ii. Depreciation Expense Ratio reveals the proportion of revenue which is spent on depreciation. It is estimated as;

$$\text{Depreciation Expense Ratio} = \frac{\text{Depreciation expense}}{\text{Gross revenue}} \times 100\%$$

The lower the Depreciation Expense Ratio the better the business operations since it implies that a lower proportion of the gross revenue is utilized on the depreciation expenses. The reverse is valid for a higher Depreciation Expense Ratio.

- iii. Net Farm Income Ratio measures the proportion of the total revenue that is not spent on any expense; hence remains as net income for business owner (s). It is estimated as;

$$\text{Net Farm Income Ratio} = \frac{\text{Net Farm Income}}{\text{Gross Revenue}} \times 100\%$$

The higher the Net Farm Income Ratio the better the business operations since it implies that a higher proportion of the gross revenue is not spent on operation expenses. Higher Net Farm Income Ratio signifies higher profitability, hence successful business operations. The reverse is valid for a lower Net Farm Income Ratio.

- iv. Production Efficiency Ratio shows the proportion of revenue that is spent on production related activities. It is estimated as:

$$\text{Production Efficiency Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Revenue}}{\text{Total Expenditure}}$$

The higher the Production Efficiency Ratio the better the business operations because it indicates excess revenue over and above production related expenditure.

Measurement of Farm Profitability

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The profitability of the poultry farmers in the study area was measured using the net income of the farmers (returns on investment). Net Farm Income (Return on Investment) is a widely patronized measure of farm profitability due to its high levels of accuracy over other indicators (Langemeier, 2020). It is estimated as; Net farm income (NFI) = Total Revenue (TR) – Total Cost (TC)

TR=Price per unit of output multiplied by quantity (output)

TC= TFC + TVC

Where: TR = Total Revenue (Gross Revenue), TC= Total Cost of Production, TFC = Total Fixed Cost, TVC = Total Variable Cost (operational cost).

Gross Margin = Gross Revenue – Fixed Cost

Measuring the Challenges Facing Poultry Farmers in the Study Area

The severity of the constraint factors confronting the poultry farmers was measured using the Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance. The Kendall's coefficient measures the degree of agreement or disagreement among constraints ranked (Amanda et al. 2013). The coefficient of concordance (w) assumes values between 0 and 1. A value of 0 signifies complete disagreement while 1 signifies perfect agreement.

The Kendall's coefficient (w) is calculated as;

$$W = \frac{12 (\sum T^2 - (\sum T)^2/N)}{NM^2(N^2 - 1)}$$

Where, N is the number of items being ranked, T is the sum of ranks for each constraint being ranked, M is the number of sets of rankings by respondents

The following hypotheses were tested to ascertain the levels of agreements or otherwise relative to the constraints confronting the poultry famers;

H₀: There exist no agreement among the farmers on the constraints facing their operations.

H₁: There exist agreement among farmers on the constraints confronting their operations.

Where H₀ and H₁ are the null and alternative hypothesis respectively

The decision rule regarding the rejection of the null hypothesis is based on the values of the test statistic. For instance, if the F calculated is greater than F critical value set then the null hypothesis is rejected.

The F calculated is the test instrument of the coefficient of significance. It is calculated as:

$$\frac{(m-1) w}{1-w}$$

Where m is number of sets of rankings by each respondent and w is the calculated coefficient of concordance.

The critical value of F has two (2) degree of freedom each for the numerator and the denominator. The degree of freedom for the numerator is;

$$Df_n = n - 2 - 2/m$$

The degree of freedom for the denominator is;

$$Df_d = m - 1[(n-2) - 2/m]$$

Where m is number of sets of rankings by each respondent and n is the number of specific constraints being ranked

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Descriptive Analysis of Survey Responses

Individual Characteristics of Respondents

The field responses showed a wide gender disparity among the respondents (Table 1). Majority (83.2%) of the respondents were male farmers with 16.8% of the respondents being female farmers (Table 1). The poultry enterprise is largely laborious hence the dominance of males over the females. In terms of age, majority (52%) of the respondents were within the age brackets of 41-50 years. The study further revealed that 24% of respondents had attained basic primary education, 36.8% had acquired secondary education, 18.4% possessed tertiary education and the remaining 20.8% of the respondents had no formal education (unlettered). The educational status of the respondents suggests that capacity building in terms of introduction of innovative and modern poultry management practices will have significant impact on the poultry egg industry. In respect of experience on the job, a vast majority (64%) of the respondents had operated their poultry enterprises for more than 5 years.

Table 1: Individual characteristics of respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	104	83.2
Female	21	16.8
Total	125	100
Age Distribution		
21 – 30	11	8.8
31 – 40	31	24.8
41 – 50	65	52.0
51 - 60	10	8.0
60+	08	6.4
Total	125	100
Educational Status		
Primary	30	24.0
Secondary	46	36.8
Tertiary	23	18.4
Unlettered	26	20.8
Total	125	100
Years of Experience		
More than 10yrs	09	7.2
5 – 10yrs	74	59.2
2 – 4yrs	26	20.8
Less than 2yrs	16	12.8
Total	125	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Estimation of Profit of Poultry Egg Production in the Study Area

Profit was estimated based on the cost of production and revenue generation associated with a production period of 24 months (the survey revealed that most of the farmers dispose off their birds as spent layers after 24 months.) Table 2 shows the fixed and variable costs incurred in the production processes. The cost variables estimated were; day-old-chicks, feeds, wages (hired labour), drugs and vaccines, veterinary services, electricity and water, transportation, depreciation of fixed assets (farm structure and equipment), and interest on borrowed funds. The study shows that poultry feeds constitute the greatest share of total expenditure. It constituted 58.54%

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of total expenditure. The high cost of poultry feed revealed in this study is consistent with the findings in the literature (Zamani et al., (2022); Etta et al., (2021); Andam et al., (2017); Tanko et al., (2014);, Hassan et al., (2011). Next to the expenditure share of poultry feeds was the cost of electricity and water constituting 11.27% of the total expenditure on production. Depreciation of fixed assets constituted 5.4% of total expenditure on production. Fixed assets (farm structures and equipment) were depreciated on the basis of the straight-line method. The costs of day-old chicks, drugs and vaccines, labor, veterinary services, transportation and interest on borrowed funds, each constituted less than 5% of the total expenditure of the farmers.

Proceeds from the sale of eggs constituted the greatest source of revenue (97.67%). Proceeds from the sale of spent layers and manure constituted 2% and 0.33% respectively. An average of GHC360,100 accrues to a farmer as gross revenue and an average gross margin of GHC169,150 per the two year production cycle. Profit (Net farm income) was calculated by subtracting the sum of fixed and variable costs from the gross income. The process yielded a net farm income of GHC152,550 indicating that poultry egg production in the study area is a profitable venture. These findings are consistent with Zamani et al. (2022) and Bukenya et al.(2021).

Table 2: Cost and revenue estimates of poultry egg production

Revenue (GH¢)	Average Cost (GH¢)	Percentage (%)
Variable Cost		
Day-old chick	4,950	2.38
Feed	121,500	58.54
Drugs and vaccines	19,500	9.40
Hired labour	7,200	3.47
Veterinary services	4,800	2.31
Electricity and water	23,400	11.27
Transportation	5,800	2.79
Others	3,800	1.83
Total Variable Cost	190,950	
Fixed Cost		
Interest on borrowed funds	5,400	2.60
Depreciation of Farm Structure	8,800	4.24
Depreciation of Farm Equipment	2,400	1.16
Total Fixed Cost	16,600	
Total Cost	207, 550	100.00
Revenue (Returns)		
Sale of Eggs	351,700	97.67
Disposal of Spent Layers	7, 200	2.00
Sale of Manure	1,200	0.33
Gross Revenue (Total Income)	360, 100	100.00
Financials		
Gross Margin	169,150	
Net Farm Income	152,550	

Source: Authors computation, 2022

Note;

Total Cost = Total Variable Cost + Total Fixed Cost

Net Farm Income= Gross Revenue – Total Cost

Percentages of fixed costs and variable costs are calculated on total cost.

The Operating Expense Ratio estimated at 0.4992 (Table 3) signifying that 49.92% of revenue generated by the

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poultry farmers was spent on operating expenses. Since the coefficient (0.4992) of the operating expenses was less than half (0.5) then the poultry farmers retained a substantial amount (more than 50%) of the revenue generated as net earnings. Similarly, the depreciation expense ratio estimated at 0.0311 implies that only 3.11% of revenue generated was used to defray the cost of depreciation on fixed assets. Since the coefficient (0.0311) was very low, it indicated that the poultry farmers maintained their fixed assets efficiently. In respect of net farm income ratio, the estimated coefficient of 0.4235 (42.35%) indicated that the poultry farmers generated excess revenue of about 57.65% on production. Also, the production efficiency ratio of 1.74 implies that for every Cedi invested on a poultry farm, there is 0.74 pesewas (74%) gross returns on the investment within the two-year (24 months) production cycle. Since the expenses ratios (Operating expenses ratio of 0.4992 and depreciation expense ratio of 0.3111) are each less than 1 (Table 3), then the poultry egg production in the study area is profitable. Furthermore, the production efficiency ratio is greater than 1 (1.74) implying that revenue exceeded cost by 74%, therefore the poultry egg production business in the study area is profitable.

Table 3: Financial Variables and Efficiency Measures

Cost Element	Amount (GHC)
A. Depreciation Expenses	11,200
B. Total Operating Expenses	190,950
C. Gross Revenue/Gross Income/Total Revenue	360,100
D. Net Farm Income	152,550
E. Total Expenditure	207,550
Financial Efficiency Measure	Ratio
Operating Expense Ratio	0.4992
Depreciation Expense Ratio	0.0311
Net Farm Income Ratio	0.4236
Production Efficiency Ratio	1.74

Source; Authors computation, 2022

Constraints of Poultry Egg Farmers in the Northern Region

The second objective of this study was to identify and describe the challenges facing poultry egg farmers in the study area. To achieve this objective, the poultry farmers were interviewed to ascertain the challenges hindering their business operations. The farmers were asked to rank the challenges in order of severity on business operations. The challenges which featured prominently were; rising cost of feeds, rising cost of day old chicks, high mortality rate, high cost of credit, harsh weather conditions (heat), inadequate extension services, poor market, and invasion of imported substitutes (imported frozen chicken). The eight (8) challenges were ranked (1-8) in order of severity of their impact on the farmers. 1 represented the most severe challenge and 8 represented the least severe one (Table 4).

Using the Kendall’s coefficient of concordance, the analysis showed a coefficient of 0.5177, F calculated of 133.21 and F critical of 2.82 at 1 percent significance level. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no agreement among poultry farmers in the Northern Region regarding the constraints militating against their operations. The Kendall’s coefficient of concordance revealed that there is significant agreement among the poultry farmers in respect of the factors militating against their operations in the study area. The constraints of the poultry farmers in the study area are discussed below:

The results showed that the most limiting constraint among the poultry egg farmers in the area is the rising cost of feeds. As of the time of the data collection (January and May, 2022), the average price of a 100 kilogram bag of maize was GH¢320. Maize remains the major feed ingredient for farmers in the study area. The farmers

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reported that the demand for maize outstripped its supply hence the rising cost of the product. They bemoaned the effect of foreigners (Nigerians and Malian traders) invading the major local markets in the region to buy maize; causing the shortages of maize in the region with the attendant consequence on price hikes. Similarly, the average price of a 50 kilogram bag of already prepared chicken-mash was GH¢240 as of the time of the data collection. Another important ingredient in the preparation of poultry feed is the protein concentrate. Furthermore, the average price of a 50 kilogram bag of protein concentrate was GH¢350. The high cost of feed ingredients is a major disincentive to the farmers since it negatively affects their profit levels. Every single respondent lamented the high price of the feeds in the last couple of years. The high cost of poultry feeds in this study is consistent with numerous studies (see, Ettah et al., (2021); Bukenya et al., (2021); Netherland Enterprise Agency (2019); Selorm (2017); Hassan et al., (2016).

Harsh weather condition was ranked as the second most limiting constraint of the poultry farmers. Characteristic of the Northern Region within the Savannah enclave, farmers experience high temperatures during the dry season, particularly between February and April each year. The farmers complained about poor egg production during the period. To remedy the negative impact of the heat on business operations, some farmers had planted trees around their farms to provide shade. Farmers admitted the positive impact of the trees in reducing the negative effect of the scorching sun on business operations.

The third most limiting constraint was high mortality rate of the birds. The farmers who recorded high mortality rates blamed the situation on interrupted power supply. Most of the farmers introduced the layers to 24 hour supply of feed for greater egg production hence the compelling need for uninterrupted power supply. The farmers reported that intermittent interruptions in the power supply causes stampede which leads to mortality rates. Interrupted power supply also compounded mortality problem, particularly among younger birds which get overcrowded at one point due to blackouts.

High cost of credit (interest on loans) was ranked the 4th most challenging constraint facing the farmers in the study area. It was revealed that some farmers run out of financial resources before the commencement of egg production. Such farmers were compelled to borrow financial resources from commercial sources (banks and private money lenders and microfinance institutions) to complement their personal savings for the business operations. The interests on borrowed funds from commercial banks ranged between 24% and 31%, per annum, between 70% and 120% for funds from private money lenders and microfinance institutions.

Imported substitutes were ranked as the 5th most challenging constraint which militated against the poultry egg farmers in the area. The farmers attributed the low prices of spent layers to the cheap imported frozen chicken from the United States of America and Brazil. In terms of meat requirements, the farmers admitted that it was cheaper to purchase the imported frozen chicken compared to their local spent layers.

Poor market for the poultry eggs was yet another bane for some farmers. It was ranked the 6th most challenging constraint facing the farmers in the study area. Whereas some of the farmers complained about low prices offered by middlemen at the farm gate, some farmers attributed the poor market for eggs in the study area to the 'dumping' practices of poultry egg producers from the Bono, Ahafo and Ashanti Regions. Admittedly, trucks loads of poultry eggs are delivered to the northern region from the southern and middle zones on weekly basis. The average price per crate of eggs from the 'invading traders' is lower than that of the poultry farmers in the study area, thereby making it difficult for the poultry egg producers in the study area to compete favourably.

Poor extension services and rising cost of day-old chicks were the less severe constraints militating against the poultry egg farmers in the study area. There were ranked 7th and 8th respectively. The farmers applauded the Regional Executives of the Poultry Farmers' Cooperative for disseminating relevant information on poultry

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farming practices to members via WhatsApp and Telegram platforms created for such purposes. The farmers did not find the cost of the day-old chicks so severe since it is one-off purchase per production cycle,. Additionally, some local poultry farmers commenced in-house hatchery as opposed to the importation of the day-old chicks from Europe and other parts of the world, thereby saving cost on the day-old chicks.

Table 4: Ranking of Constraints Facing the Poultry Farmers

Constraints	Sum of rank	Rank
High Cost of Feed	186	1 st
Harsh weather condition	387	2 nd
High mortality rate	404	3 rd
High cost of credit	597	4 th
Imported Substitute	651	5 th
Poor market	658	6 th
Poor extension services	805	7 th
High cost of day-old chicks	818	8 th

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Conclusions

We analysed the profitability and financial efficiency of poultry egg farmers in selected districts of the Northern Region. We also investigated the challenges which hinder the operations of the farmers in the area. The study revealed that poultry egg farming in the selected districts of the Northern Region is profitable as indicated by the average gross margin of GH¢ 169,150 and an average net farm income of GH¢ 152, 550 over a two-year production cycle. Also, the coefficients of the financial ratios amply demonstrate the profitability of the poultry egg production in the area. However, the recent overall price hikes in the country as a result of the depreciation of the Cedi with its attendant consequences of rising fuel prices leave the farmers in a difficult situation. As underscored by the descriptive statistics, the serious constraints confronting the poultry egg farmers in the area in order of severity are; high cost of feeds, harsh weather conditions, high mortality rate, high cost of credit, cheap imported substitutes, poor market, poor extension and rising cost of day-old chicks. The cost build-up suggests that cost of feeds, electricity and water, drugs and vaccines were the most serious cost items representing 79.21% of the total cost of production. There is a looming danger of closure of farms if the rising cost of poultry feeds continues unabated. Government intervention is necessary to curtail any unwanted labour turnover in the industry.

The poultry egg sub-sector holds a key to reducing unemployment among youth in the region and the nation at large.

On the basis of the findings, it is recommended that government focuses greater attention on the poultry industry in the region and the nation at large to provide sustainable self-employable jobs to the teeming unemployed youth. Extension services are essential to sharpen the skills of poultry egg farmers. Potential poultry egg farmers could be offered the necessary training in poultry egg production. They could be assisted with start-up capital at concessionary interest rates to commence operation. Government should consider subsidies on the key inputs of the farmers.

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